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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation Of A Novel Polyherbal Shampoo

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ABSTRACT

This study presents the formulation and evaluation of a novel polyherbal shampoo designed to leverage the beneficial properties of various natural ingredients. A total of three formulations were developed using the decoction method, incorporating key herbal components such as Hibiscus, Neem, Amla, Aloe Vera, and Shikakai. Each formulation underwent comprehensive physicochemical evaluations, including assessments of physical appearance, pH, solid content, foaming ability, foam stability, dirt dispersion, skin sensitization, and stability studies. The results revealed that all formulations exhibited a dark brown color and pleasant rose-like odor, with formulation F3 identified as the optimized variant. F3 demonstrated a pH of 5.32, closely matching the scalp's natural pH, and contained a solid content of 11.75%. Foaming ability and stability assessments showed that F3 produced a small, dense foam with superior performance compared to F1 and F2. Moreover, it effectively dispersed dirt while being non-irritating to the skin and scalp. Stability studies indicated that F3 remained stable for two months, with no significant changes in its physicochemical properties. In conclusion, the F3 polyherbal shampoo not only exhibits favorable stability and activity but also highlights the potential of combining herbal ingredients in effective hair care formulations, catering to the growing consumer preference for natural products.

INTRODUCTION

Herbal formulations have seen an unprecedented rise in popularity in recent years, largely due to their association with safety, biocompatibility, and numerous therapeutic benefits when compared to synthetic products. Within the personal care industry, shampoos hold an essential place as they

play a crucial role in maintaining scalp hygiene, improving hair quality, and addressing various hair disorders. However, conventional shampoos often comprise harsh chemical surfactants, preservatives, and synthetic additives that can lead to adverse effects such as scalp irritation, hair dryness, and in some cases, environmental toxicity

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due to the presence of non-biodegradable ingredients.¹⁻³ These growing concerns have prompted a significant shift towards the development of polyherbal shampoos, which utilize natural plant-based ingredients renowned for their medicinal, therapeutic, and cosmetic properties.⁴⁻⁷ Shampoos are primarily formulated as hair care products designed to cleanse the scalp and hair by removing dirt, excess sebum, and environmental pollutants. Traditional synthetic shampoos typically contain detergents, additives, foaming agents, and preservatives, aimed at providing effective cleaning without completely stripping the hair of its natural oils. While these products continue to dominate the global market, there has been an increasing trend toward the use of herbal shampoos, largely driven by consumer demand for natural alternatives. The preference for herbal shampoos stems from their minimal side effects, eco-friendly profiles, and perceived gentleness, making them suitable for long-term use. However, the formulation of herbal shampoos presents unique challenges. Achieving the foaming, detergency, consistency, and shelf life comparable to their synthetic counterparts is often complex when only natural ingredients are used.⁷⁻⁹ Polyherbal shampoos combine the power of multiple herbal ingredients, leveraging their synergistic properties to offer a holistic solution to scalp and hair care. Herbs like *Aloe vera*, *Shikakai* (*Acacia concinna*), *Reetha* (*Sapindus mukorossi*), and *Neem* (*Azadirachta indica*) have long been celebrated in traditional medicine systems such as Ayurveda for their effectiveness in treating hair and scalp conditions.¹⁰ These herbs possess a diverse array of pharmacological properties, including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and cleansing activities, making them ideal candidates for the formulation of herbal shampoos. *Aloe vera*, for instance, is known for its moisturizing and soothing effects on the scalp, while *Shikakai* is a natural cleanser that promotes

hair growth. *Reetha*, a natural foaming agent, gently cleanses the scalp, and *Neem* provides strong antimicrobial benefits, helping to prevent dandruff and other scalp infections.¹¹⁻¹⁴ The present study aims to formulate and evaluate a novel polyherbal shampoo that harnesses the therapeutic potential of multiple herbs, focusing on promoting scalp health, improving hair texture, and reducing hair fall. By scientifically validating the use of these herbal ingredients, the study also seeks to evaluate the physicochemical properties, safety, and efficacy of the developed shampoo formulation. This research holds particular significance against the backdrop of an increasing global demand for natural, eco-friendly beauty products that not only meet consumer expectations for safety but also offer additional therapeutic benefits without the negative side effects associated with chemical-based alternatives. Polyherbal shampoos align with the ongoing shift towards sustainable and organic beauty products, emphasizing the relevance of this study to both the scientific community and the cosmetic industry. Moreover, the interest in green chemistry and environmentally sustainable cosmetic formulations is on the rise, further establishing the importance of exploring herbal alternatives in hair care.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ The objective of this study is to develop a polyherbal shampoo by selecting appropriate herbal ingredients based on their traditional and pharmacological efficacy. Following the formulation, the shampoo will be subjected to a series of evaluations, including physicochemical properties such as pH, viscosity, foam stability, and antimicrobial activity. The study's ultimate goal is to assess the formulation's potential for commercialization as a safe and effective alternative to synthetic shampoos, offering a comprehensive understanding of its capabilities and benefits.¹⁸

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

MATERIALS:

The materials used in the formulation of the novel polyherbal shampoo were carefully selected to combine both traditional herbal ingredients and modern excipients, ensuring optimal efficacy, safety, and cosmetic appeal. Several key herbal components, including *Hibiscus*, *Neem*, *Aloe vera*, *Banyan*, *Soy milk*, *Curry*, and *Fenugreek*, were prepared from homemade sources, highlighting the use of natural, fresh ingredients traditionally known for their hair and scalp benefits. These homemade ingredients were chosen based on their established therapeutic properties in hair care, ensuring the formulation remains rooted in traditional knowledge. Other ingredients, such as *Amla*, were sourced from reputable herbal manufacturers like Patanjali, while *Shikakai* and *Ritha* were purchased from an Ayurvedic store, ensuring the inclusion of widely recognized Ayurvedic herbs known for their cleansing and conditioning properties. These herbs are integral to the formulation, offering benefits such as hair strengthening and promoting scalp health.

Specialized excipients, including *Guar gum* and *Xanthan gum*, were provided by DJP's College of Pharmacy, Pohetakali. These ingredients serve essential roles as thickening and stabilizing agents, contributing to the shampoo's consistency and user experience. *Almond oil* from Raw Valley and *Rose water* from Dabur were incorporated for their nourishing, moisturizing, and soothing properties, further enhancing the cosmetic and therapeutic effects of the shampoo. This meticulous selection of both natural and commercially available ingredients ensures that the polyherbal shampoo is not only effective but also safe and appealing for regular use.

METHODS:

Formulation of Polyherbal Shampoo:

Preparation of Soy Milk:

The preparation of soy milk for use in the formulation of the polyherbal shampoo involved several key steps to ensure a smooth and consistent extract. Initially, 200 grams of soybean seeds were soaked in 1000 ml of water for 8 to 10 hours to soften them. After soaking, the seeds were thoroughly washed to remove any impurities. The softened seeds were then ground with water to form slurry. This slurry was heated for 10 to 15 minutes, allowing it to blend effectively and release its nutrients. After heating, the mixture was filtered to separate the solid residues from the liquid. The filtrate, which is the soy milk, was collected and then boiled for a few additional minutes to ensure proper extraction and consistency before being incorporated into the polyherbal shampoo formulation.¹⁹⁻²⁵

Preparation method of polyherbal shampoo:

The polyherbal shampoo was prepared using the decoction method, following a systematic process. First, all the ingredients were weighed according to the formulation. A decoction was prepared by boiling *Hibiscus*, *Neem*, *Amla*, *Banyan root* powders, *Aloe vera gel*, *soy milk*, *curry leaves*, and *fenugreek seeds* in one portion of water. After boiling, the mixture was filtered through muslin cloth, and the filtrate was collected. Similarly, a separate decoction of *Shikakai* and *Ritha* was prepared in another portion of water and filtered using muslin cloth to collect the filtrate. The two filtrates were then mixed together with constant stirring to ensure uniformity. To achieve the desired consistency similar to that of a semi-solid shampoo, *guar gum* was added as a thickening agent. *Preservatives* and *perfume* was added lastly. This step ensured that the polyherbal shampoo maintained an appropriate texture for ease of application.²⁶⁻³²

Table 1: Formulation Table of polyherbal shampoo

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3
Hibiscus	5	5	5
Neem	5	5	5
Curry leaves	5	5	5
Amla	10	10	10
Shikakai	15	15	15
Ritha	15	20	25
Aloe vera	10	10	10
Banyan	5	5	5
Soy milk	20	20	20
Fenugreek	5	5	5
Rose water	5	5	5
Almond oil	4	4	4
Guar gum	1	-	-
Chitosan	-	1.5	-
Tragacanth	-	-	2

Figure 1: Method of preparation**Figure 2: Herbal shampoo**

Evaluation of Polyherbal Shampoo

To assess the quality and effectiveness of the prepared polyherbal shampoo, several evaluation tests were conducted, focusing on visual characteristics and physicochemical parameters such as pH, foam stability, and solid content.³³⁻⁴⁵

Physical Appearance and Visual Assessment

The formulations were visually inspected for clarity, foam-producing ability, color, and odor. These attributes provide an initial qualitative evaluation of the shampoo's aesthetic and sensory qualities.

pH Determination

The pH of the shampoo was measured by preparing a 10% w/v solution in distilled water. For the test, 1.5 ml of shampoo was placed in a

beaker, and water was added to a total volume of 15 ml. After allowing the solution to stand for 30 minutes at room temperature, the pH was measured using pH paper. This test ensures the shampoo's pH is compatible with scalp and hair, reducing the risk of irritation.

Figure 3: pH Determination

Determination of Solid Content

To determine the percentage of solid content, 4 grams of the polyherbal shampoo was weighed into a clean, dry evaporating dish. The dish was heated on a hot plate to evaporate the liquid component. After complete evaporation, the remaining solids were weighed. The percentage of solids was calculated using the formula:

$$\% \text{ Solid Content} = \frac{\text{Mass of solid}}{\text{Total mass of solution}} \times 100$$

This test is important for assessing the concentration and stability of the formulation.

Figure 4: % Solid Content

Foaming Ability and Foam Stability

The foaming ability and stability of the shampoo were evaluated using the cylinder shake method. A 1% shampoo solution (50 ml) was added to a 250 ml graduated cylinder, sealed, and shaken 10 times. The volume of foam produced was measured immediately after shaking and at 1-minute intervals for 4 minutes. Foam stability is critical for consumer satisfaction and shampoo efficacy.

Dirt Dispersion Test

To assess the shampoo's cleansing power, 2 drops of shampoo were added to 10 ml of distilled water in a large test tube. After adding one drop of ink, the tube was shaken 10 times. The amount of ink dispersed in the foam was evaluated and categorized as none, light, moderate, or heavy. This test helps determine the shampoo's ability to remove dirt and impurities from hair and scalp.

Figure 5: Dirt Dispersion

Skin Sensitization Test

The skin sensitization test was conducted on human volunteers to ensure the shampoo does not cause irritation. Volunteers applied the shampoo on their skin to check for any signs of irritation or allergic reactions.

Stability Test

The stability of the polyherbal shampoo was assessed by evaluating the organoleptic properties, including odor and color, over a storage period of 2 months. The stability test confirmed that the formulation remained chemically and physically stable during this period, ensuring its suitability for long-term use. These evaluation tests collectively demonstrate the effectiveness, safety, and stability of the polyherbal shampoo, providing a foundation for its potential commercial application.

Result and Discussion:

Physical Appearance

The physical characteristics of the polyherbal shampoo formulations were visually assessed, focusing on attributes such as color, odor, and homogeneity. All three formulations (F1, F2, and F3) displayed a consistent dark brown color, indicative of the natural herbal ingredients used. The formulations exhibited a rose-like fragrance, contributing to their sensory appeal. Additionally, no phase separation was observed, confirming the stability and uniformity of the mixtures. Each formulation demonstrated good foaming ability, a crucial factor for effective cleansing performance in shampoos. Overall, the polyherbal shampoos showed an aesthetically pleasing appearance with desirable physical properties.

Table 2: Physical Appearance

Formulation	Colour	Odour	Foaming ability
F1	Dark brown	Rose like	Good
F2	Dark brown	Rose like	Good
F3	Dark brown	Rose like	Good

PH Determination

The pH determination of the polyherbal shampoo formulations was carried out to ensure their compatibility with the scalp and hair. The pH values for all formulations were found to be within the range of 5.30 to 5.70, which is ideal for maintaining the natural pH balance of the scalp.

Specifically, formulation F1 had a pH of 5.40, F2 measured 5.69, and F3 showed a pH of 5.32. This mildly acidic pH range aligns with the typical pH of healthy hair and skin, helping to prevent scalp irritation while maintaining the integrity of the hair's protective layer.

Table 3: PH Determination

Formulation	PH of polyherbal shampoo
F1	5.40
F2	5.69
F3	5.32

% Solid Content

The percentage of solid content in the polyherbal shampoo formulations was measured to assess the concentration of solid ingredients present in each formulation. A higher solid content generally indicates a thicker consistency, which can affect the shampoo's performance, such as foaming

ability and ease of application. In the three formulations, F1 had 14% solid content, F2 had the highest at 16.75%, and F3 had the lowest at 11.75%. These variations in solid content could influence the texture and thickness of each formulation, contributing to differences in their overall effectiveness.

Table 4: % solid Content

Formulation	% Solid Content
F1	14 %
F2	16.75 %
F3	11.75 %

Foaming Ability and Foaming Stability

Table 5 shows the foaming ability and stability of the polyherbal shampoo formulations were assessed using the Cylinder shake method over four minutes. Initially, F1 and F3 produced 110 ml of foam, while F2 generated 100 ml. throughout the assessment, foam volume decreased for all

formulations, with F1 maintaining the highest level at 90 ml by the fifth minute, compared to F2 at 88 ml and F3 at 98 ml. These results indicate that F1 exhibited superior initial foaming ability and stability, which are essential for acceptance as they enhance the perceived cleansing efficacy of the shampoo.

Table 5: Foaming ability and foaming stability

Time in minutes	Volume of foam (ml)		
	F1	F2	F3
01	110	100	110
02	105	97	110
03	100	95	106

04	95	90	100
05	90	88	98

Foam Type

All three polyherbal shampoo formulations—F1, F2, and F3—produced foam characterized as small and dense. This foam type is favorable, indicating high quality and effective cleansing properties. The uniformity across formulations suggests that the chosen ingredients contributed positively to the foaming characteristics and satisfaction.

Table 6: Foam types

Formulation	Foam Type
F1	Small and dense
F2	Small and dense
F3	Small and dense

Dirt Dispersion Test

Table 7 shows the Dirt Dispersion Test assessed the ability of each polyherbal shampoo formulation to disperse dirt, indicated by the amount of ink mixed into the foam. Formulations F1 and F3 showed light dirt dispersion, suggesting moderate cleansing effectiveness, while F2 demonstrated heavy dirt dispersion, indicating a stronger cleaning capacity. This highlights a trade-off between effective dirt removal and gentleness, with F1 and F3 being more suitable for sensitive scalps.

Table 7: Dirt Dispersion Test

Formulation	Amount of Dirt Dispersion
F1	Light
F2	Heavy
F3	Light

Skin Sensitization Test

Table 8 shows the Skin Sensitization Test assessed the polyherbal shampoo formulations for skin irritation. All formulations—F1, F2, and F3—showed no signs of irritation, indicating their safety for use. This is especially important as the shampoos contain natural ingredients, making them suitable for a wide range of consumers, including those with sensitive skin.

Table 8: Skin Sensitization Test

Formulation	Observation
F1	No irritation on skin
F2	No irritation on skin
F3	No irritation on skin

Stability Study

Table 9 shows the stability study evaluated the polyherbal shampoo formulations over two months. Formulations F1 and F3 remained stable, showing no significant changes, while formulation F2 displayed signs of instability. These results emphasize the importance of stability testing in ensuring product reliability and safety.

Table 9: Stability Studies

Formulation	Observation
F1	Stable after 2 months
F2	Not so stable
F3	Stable after 2 months

CONCLUSION

Herbal formulations are increasingly favored due to their perceived safety and reduced side effects compared to synthetic products, leading to a rising demand in the global market. This study focused on the development of a polyherbal shampoo that combines various hair-beneficial ingredients into a single formulation. Three batches of polyherbal shampoo were prepared and subjected to a range of physicochemical evaluations, including physical appearance, pH, solid content, foaming ability, foam stability, dirt dispersion, skin sensitivity, and stability assessments. Among the formulations, F3 emerged as the optimized option. It exhibited a clear, dark brown appearance with a pleasant rose-like fragrance. The pH of F3 was measured at 5.32, closely aligning with the natural pH of the scalp, and its solid content was approximately 11.75%. Notably, F3 demonstrated superior foaming ability and stability compared to F1 and F2, producing small, dense foam and effectively dispersing dirt. Importantly, F3 was found to be non-irritating to the skin and scalp.

Stability studies conducted at room temperature confirmed that the formulation remained stable over a two-month period, with no significant changes in its physicochemical properties. In conclusion, the F3 polyherbal shampoo displays promising stability and efficacy, positioning it as a viable alternative in the hair care market.

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